

Enhancing efficiency and stability in CPT systems: a state feedback controller approach

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ABSTRACT

This work aims to present an innovative design and simulation of an auto-tuning capacitive power transfer (CPT) system. The system utilizes a Class-E converter, renowned for its exceptional efficiency. Challenges arise when trying to regulate the output voltage of a Class-E converter in the presence of load fluctuations, leading to an escalation in switching losses. By employing first harmonic approximation (FHA) and generalized state space averaging (GSSA), a state-space model of the system is constructed to effectively address this problem. The output voltage is regulated by a state feedback controller developed using the Lyapunov approach. This paper presents a comparative analysis of a traditional PID controller and a recently suggested state feedback controller, with a primary emphasis on system stabilization. The study examines the similarities and differences between the two controllers. The efficacy of the proposed controller design is demonstrated through the utilization of simulation data. Furthermore, these results confirm the validity of the comparative study, making it a substantial contribution to the field of CPT systems.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Wireless power transfer (WPT) is attractive since it provides electricity without the need for connections. Inductive power transfer (IPT) is frequently employed for WPT, but its limitations result in decreased system efficiency. IPT systems are impacted by eddy current losses [1], which to exist despite attempts to decrease their occurrence [2]. On the other hand, capacitive power transfer (CPT) systems utilize electric fields rather than magnetic fields to deliver power. CPT systems exhibit cost-effectiveness, reduced weight, and superior performance in handling misalignment compared to IPT systems [3]. CPT systems effectively decrease electromagnetic interference (EMI) by confining electric fields mostly within electrically conductive surfaces [4].

However, CPT system has a high level of sensitivity to variations in both load and the separation distance between the plates [5], [6]. To deal with this sensitivity, researchers have suggested using compensation networks that can improve the efficiency of the system by converting the input impedance into a single resistive point even when there are changes in coupling [7], [8]. Several compensation topologies, including inductor, inductor-capacitor, inductor-capacitor-inductor or L, LC, and LCL, have been investigated to enhance CPT performance [9]. Nevertheless, these networks also pose difficulties, such as heightened

intricacy and potential decline in performance under different circumstances, highlighting the necessity for alternate methods to uphold system stability and effectiveness. In ongoing CPT research, researchers are researching compensation topologies to boost power and efficiency [10], [11]. CPT can now be used in high-power electric vehicle charging systems and low-power biomedical implants [12], [13]. However, compensation networks can increase losses, reducing system efficiency [14].

The variability of circuit characteristics, such as mutual inductance or coupling capacitance, presents substantial hurdles in practical WPT applications. Differences in characteristics can cause the resonance frequency to deviate, resulting in a reduction in the ability to transfer power and overall efficiency. In IPT systems, these challenges have been resolved by using optimized compensation networks, such as LCL and CLC topologies [15], [16] and employing advanced control methods, such as resilient H_∞ controllers [17], [18]. Although IPT and CPT systems share commonalities in their modeling, CPT systems face more significant difficulties because of their intrinsically low coupling capacitance [19]. Therefore, it is necessary to have controllers that improve resilience. However, most current CPT controllers only concentrate on achieving impedance-matching [20], [21].

Motivated by the above concerns and drawbacks, this article aims to design a reliable controller that improves CPT system stability in the face of load variation. This article uses generalized state-space averaging (GSSA) and frequency-harmonic analysis (FHA) to model the system. A linear state space model is generated by linearizing the nonlinear system by its steady-state operating point. The main contribution of this paper can be summarized as:

- Novel approach: This paper presents a new method for voltage regulation in Class-E converters of CPT systems using a Lyapunov-based controller, offering a fresh perspective on CPT system efficiency and stability.
- Empirical validation: The paper provides simulation results that confirm the effectiveness of the Lyapunov controller, serving as a valuable reference for future studies.
- Practical impact: The research potentially enhances CPT system efficiency and stability, impacting WPT applications significantly.

The remainder of the paper is arranged as section 2 analysis of Class-E CPT is done. Section 3 presents the modeling procedure that was used to obtain the system's state space model. The Lyapunov approach-based state feedback control design is shown in section 4. Section 5 presents an illustration of the simulation outcome, while section 6 presents the conclusion.

2. ANALYSIS AND MODELLING OF CLASS E CPT

In this section, we begin by constructing the initial harmonic model of the CPT system using Class-E topology, utilizing FHA. After that, a linearization procedure is performed at the system's operating point, which leads to the creation of a linear state-space model for the CPT system based on Class-E. Figure 1(a) shows the schematic diagram of the Class-E-based CPT system, while Figure 1(b) depicts the system's equivalent circuit.

The resonant capacitor, C_S , represents the equivalent capacitance formed by the series combination of capacitors, C_{S1} and C_{S2} , while the resistance R_t accounts for the total resistance of the loaded full-wave rectifier, as detailed in [22]. The equations related to C_S and R_t are shown in (1). The calculations provided here were comprehensively detailed in references [23], [24].

$$C_S = \frac{C_{S1} * C_{S2}}{C_{S1} + C_{S2}}, R_t = \frac{8 * R_l}{\pi^2} \quad (1)$$

The assumptions for the CPT system are consistent with the assumptions outlined in [25], while depending on [26], the calculations used to determine the values of the components in Figure 1 are as follow: the output power of the system, P_o is calculated using the (2).

$$P_o = \frac{8V_{cc}}{(\pi^2 + 4)R_t} \quad (2)$$

the resonant inductance, L_t , was separated into two components, L_{ext} and L_{res} , which were computed using the (3).

$$L_t = \frac{1.153 R_t}{w} + \frac{QR_t}{w} \quad (3)$$

where, Q is the quality factor, and the w is the switching frequency. C_p , and C_s are the shunt capacitance and the resonant capacitance respectively, both can be obtained as in (4).

$$C_p = \frac{P_o}{\pi w V_{cc}^2}, C_s = \frac{1}{wQR_t} \tag{4}$$

The chock inductor's minimum value is calculated as in (5).

$$L_{c.min} = 2 \left(\frac{\pi^2}{4} + 1 \right) \frac{R_t}{f} \tag{5}$$

Figure 1. Class-E-based CPT system of (a) schematic diagram and (b) equivalent circuit

3. DYNAMIC MODELLING OF CLASS-E CPT SYSTEM

In this section, the state space representation of the Class-E CPT is obtained, followed by performing linearization to derive the linearized state matrix, input matrix, and output matrix of the system. The modelling procedure employs the FHA, assuming that only the fundamental harmonic contributes to the power transfer. Through the utilization of Fourier series expansion, the first harmonic of the series current (denoted as i) passing through L_t and C_s , as well as the voltage V_{cs} applied to capacitor C_s , can be expressed in accordance with the FHA. Where i_s , i_c , v_s , and v_c are the Fourier coefficients for representing i and V_{cs} respectively. By differentiating both side of (6), we obtained (7).

$$\begin{cases} i = i_s \sin wt + i_c \cos wt \\ v_{cs} = v_s \sin wt + v_c \cos wt \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{di}{dt} = \left(\frac{di_s}{dt} - wi_c \right) \sin(wt) + \left(\frac{di_c}{dt} + wi_s \right) \cos(wt) \\ \frac{dv_{cs}}{dt} = \left(\frac{dv_s}{dt} - wv_c \right) \sin(wt) + \left(\frac{dv_c}{dt} + wv_s \right) \cos(wt) \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

By analyzing the equivalent circuit in Figure 1(b) using KVL, and KCL, the (8) are obtained.

$$\begin{cases} V_{AB} = L_t \frac{di}{dt} + V_{cs} + \operatorname{sgn}(i) V_f \\ i = C_s \frac{dv_{cs}}{dt} \\ |i| = C_f \frac{dv_f}{dt} + \frac{v_f}{R_l} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

In (8), V_{AB} represents the voltage across the shunt capacitor C_p , while C_f , denotes the system's output voltage. The function $\operatorname{sgn}(x)$, denotes the signum function and it is given in (9).

$$\operatorname{sgn}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & x < 0 \\ 0 & x = 0 \\ -1 & x > 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

According to Wang *et al.* [27], the symbol, $\operatorname{sgn}(x)$ is approximate as in (10).

$$\begin{cases} \operatorname{sgn}(i) = \frac{4i_s}{\pi i_p} \sin(\omega t) + \frac{4i_c}{\pi i_p} \cos(\omega t) \\ |i| \approx \frac{2}{\pi} i_p \\ i_p = \sqrt{i_s^2 + i_c^2} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The voltage across MOSFET, V_{AB} , is expressed as in (11).

$$V_{ab} = \begin{cases} \frac{I_o}{\omega C_p} \left[\omega t - \frac{3\pi}{2} - \frac{\pi}{2} \cos(\omega t) - \sin(\omega t) \right] & \pi < \omega t < 2\pi \\ 0 & 0 < \omega t < \pi \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The Fourier series expansion of the voltage V_{AB} is simplified as in (12),

$$V_{AB} = a_1 \sin(\omega t) + b_1 \cos(\omega t) \quad (12)$$

where a_1 and b_1 are formulated as in (13).

$$\begin{cases} a_1 = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{\pi}^{2\pi} v_{AB} \sin(\omega t) d(\omega t) = -\frac{\pi V_{CC}}{2} \\ b_1 = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{\pi}^{2\pi} v_{AB} \cos(\omega t) d(\omega t) = \frac{(8-\pi^2)V_{CC}}{4} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

By substituting (6), (7), (10), (12), and (13) into (8), and then setting the coefficients of the DC, sine, and cosine terms equal to each other, the state-space equation can be derived as in (14).

$$\begin{cases} L_t \frac{di_s}{dt} = L_t \omega i_c - v_s - \frac{4i_s}{\pi i_p} v_f - \frac{\pi V_{CC}}{2} \\ L_t \frac{di_c}{dt} = -L_t \omega i_s - v_c - \frac{4i_c}{\pi i_p} v_f + \frac{(8-\pi^2)V_{CC}}{4} \\ C_s \frac{dv_s}{dt} = i_s + C_s \omega v_c \\ C_s \frac{dv_c}{dt} = i_c - C_s \omega v_s \\ C_f \frac{dv_f}{dt} = \frac{2}{\pi} i_p - \frac{v_f}{R_l} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

In steady state, $\frac{2}{\pi} I_p - \frac{v_f}{R_l} = 0$, where I_p and V_f are the steady state value of i_p and v_f . Hence, (14) can be expressed as follows:

$$A_{SS} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{8R_l}{\pi^2 L_t} & \omega & -\frac{1}{L_t} & 0 \\ -\omega & -\frac{8R_l}{\pi^2 L_t} & 0 & -\frac{1}{L_t} \\ \frac{1}{C_s} & 0 & 0 & \omega \\ 0 & \frac{1}{C_s} & -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad B_{SS} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\pi V_{CC}}{2L_t} \\ \frac{(8-\pi^2)V_{CC}}{4L_t} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The equilibrium point is determined when $\dot{x} = 0$, which yields $x_0 = -A^{-1}BV_{CC}$. Performing linearization of (14) around this equilibrium point provides the linearized state matrix, input matrix, and output matrix of the system, we arrive at (15).

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{4I_c^2 V_f}{\pi L_t I_p^3} & w_0 + \frac{4I_c I_s V_f}{\pi L_t I_p^3} & -\frac{1}{L} & 0 & -\frac{4I_s}{\pi L_t I_p} \\ \frac{4I_c I_s V_f}{\pi L_t I_p^3} - w_0 & -\frac{4I_c^2 V_f}{\pi L_t I_p^3} & 0 & -\frac{1}{L} & -\frac{4I_c}{\pi L_t I_p} \\ \frac{1}{C_s} & 0 & 0 & w_0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{C_s} & -w_0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{2I_s}{\pi C_p I_p} & \frac{2I_c}{\pi C_p I_p} & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{R_l C_f} \end{bmatrix}, B = \begin{bmatrix} I_c \\ -I_s \\ V_c \\ -V_c \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, C = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (15)$$

4. STATE FEEDBACK CONTROL DESIGN

The main part of the control design is a state feedback (SF) controller based on the Lyapunov approach. The SF controller adjusts the switching frequency of the Class-E converter according to the state variables of the CPT system, so the output voltage is regulated, and the system stability is ensured. To ensure zero steady state error, the system is enhanced by incorporating an integrator state. The overall controller design based on the Lyapunov approach is depicted in Figure 2, where C_g is the controller gain. Consider the following system as in (16).

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = Ax + Bu \\ y = Cx \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

The state of integrator is introduced as in (17).

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = Ax + C_g B \alpha \\ \dot{\alpha} = u \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Hence, the system state equation with the integrator's state becomes as in (18).

$$\begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{\alpha} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & C_g B \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ \alpha \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} u \\ y = [C \quad 0] \begin{bmatrix} x \\ \alpha \end{bmatrix} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

So, the linearized system now becomes the (19).

$$A_l = \begin{bmatrix} A & C_g B \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, B_l = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, C_l = [C \quad 0] \quad (19)$$

A Lyapunov is introduced as in (20)

$$V = x^T P x \quad (20)$$

where P is the Lyapunov matrix that will satisfy the following condition as in (21) and (22).

$$V(x) > 0 \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{dv}{dx} \leq 0 \quad (22)$$

The controller is selected to be on the form of (23),

$$u = -Kx \quad (23)$$

where the K is the gain value of the controller.

Figure 2. Block diagram of the controller design

- Theorem 1

By formulating the Lyapunov equation and employing calculus theory to simplify it along with its associated conditions, we have derived the following linear matrix inequality (LMI) equation. Moreover, it is worth noting that the system can be stabilized through state feedback if and only if $\begin{bmatrix} X \\ \dot{X} \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B^T & C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X \\ \dot{X} \end{bmatrix} \leq 0$ is met.

- Proof of the Theorem 1

According to (22), the differentiation of V should be less than zero and as known from the Lyapunov in (20).

$$V = x^T P x$$

$$\frac{d(x^T P x)}{dx} = \dot{X}^T P X + X^T P \dot{X} \leq 0$$

$$\frac{d(x^T P x)}{dx} = X^T (A^T P + A P - K^T B^T P - P B K) X \leq 0$$

From this, you can infer that A, and B value are as follow:

$$A = (A^T P + P A)$$

$$B = -(P B K + K^T B^T P)$$

Converting Lyapunov function to matrix form using Schur complement, one arrives at:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X \\ \dot{X} \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} A^T P + P A & -(P B K + K^T B^T P) \\ -(P B K + K^T B^T P)^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X \\ \dot{X} \end{bmatrix} \leq 0$$

The proof is completed.

5. SIMULATION RESULT

This section discusses the effectiveness of the proposed method. The simulation work is done using the following specifications:

$$V_{cc} = 24V, R_l = 40 \Omega, f = 2MHz, Q = 20, C_f = 20 \mu F, V_o = 14.4V, C_{s1}, C_{s2} = 245.38 pF,$$

$$C_p = 453 pF, L_t = 54.55 \mu H, L_{c_min} = 138.7 \mu F$$

A complete CPT system, employing the Class-E converter and incorporating an automatic frequency tuning mechanism, has been realized within the MATLAB environment, utilizing the sim electronics package within Simulink. The schematic representation of the system is delineated in Figure 3.

For this design, it is necessary to keep the system output voltage steady at 14.4 V. Following the design procedure of our Lyapunov controller present in section 4, the Lyapunov matrix and control gain is calculated by employing YALMIP tools in MATLAB and obtained as follow:

$$\text{Lyapunov matrix, } P = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9001 & -0.1646 & -0.0002 & -0.0002 & -0.0275 \\ -0.1646 & 0.7340 & 0.0000 & 0.0003 & -0.0009 \\ -0.0002 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 \\ -0.0002 & 0.0003 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 \\ -0.0275 & -0.0009 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.1974 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\text{control gain, } K = [2.804 \quad -1.768 \quad -0.002644 \quad -0.00406 \quad 68.0083]$$

For this simulation, the open-loop signal is impacted when altering the load by +30% at 4 ms and -30% at 10 ms. The proposed controller is then compared with PID controller. The comparison is shown in Figure 4 between the proposed one and with open loop and PID. The performance of the proposed controller when compared with PID controller is shown in Table 1.

Figure 3. Auto frequency tuning Class-E CPT system

Figure 4. Open loop vs PID and Lyapunov

Table 1. The performance of Lyapunov vs PID

Term	Lyapunov	PID
Settling time (ms)	0.05	2.7
Overshoot	0.4	1.437
Steady-state error	0.3	0.3

6. CONCLUSION

This study presents a comprehensive analysis of CPT systems, with a particular emphasis on the integration of SF into the design of Class E inverters. Utilizing the GSSA method and MATLAB simulations, a thorough evaluation of CPT system performance is conducted. Drawing inspiration from successful Lyapunov-based SF controllers in similar CPT configurations, the investigation is extended to incorporate widely used PID controllers. The Lyapunov-based SF controllers exhibit remarkable robustness against load variations, thereby ensuring stable output voltages. These controllers, developed through principled Lyapunov techniques, demonstrate resilience in the face of diverse disturbances, affirming their effectiveness in maintaining system stability. In conclusion, this paper contributes to the field by providing insights into the efficacy of Lyapunov-based SF controllers in CPT systems. The findings offer valuable considerations for engineers and researchers seeking optimal control strategies in similar energy transfer systems. As progress is made towards more efficient and reliable CPT systems, the findings presented serve as a stepping stone for future advancements in controller design and application.

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